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Review Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL LIP GLOSSJilsha G^{*1}, Elna Abi², Rubeena S³, Samitha T S⁴, Sneha S⁵¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Sanjo College of Pharmaceutical studies, Vellapara ,
Palakkad 678702, Kerala^{2,3,4,5}Department of Pharmaceutics, Sanjo College of Pharmaceutical studies, Vellapara ,
Palakkad 678702, Kerala**Abstract:**

Human beings are obsessed with looking beautiful. Cosmetics are widely used products among almost all age groups to look elegant and young. Herbal Cosmetics are formulated using one or more herbal ingredients which are added to provide defined cosmetic benefits only are called "Herbal Cosmetics". The main rationale of our study was to compare synthetic and herbal cosmetics, further focusing on the formulation aspects and marketing studies of Herbal lip gloss. As a part of this collation, we have gathered information regarding the adverse effects of various cosmetic preparations having necessary roles in our habitual life and justify the need for replacement of these synthetic cosmetics with herbal. Furthermore, herbal ingredients with distinguished therapeutic effects were sorted as an alternative to harmful synthetic cosmetic ingredients. A Market study of lip gloss was performed and a commendable expansion of Lip gloss market growth over the years is presented with evidence. Data regarding the anticipated demand for herbal beauty products are also documented. Lip care products on an everyday basis contain harmful heavy metals and preservatives. Other than leaching through the pores on your lips, these heavy metals and other chemicals can also be accidentally ingested. Lead affects the heart and brain, Cadmium and Chromium can cause cancer, and Preservatives could cause breast cancer. Lip glosses are applied to the lips to provide a glossy finish and sometimes color. Herbal lip gloss makes the lip glossy, nourishes the lips, and protects lips from the effects of harmful chemicals. By employing these data, we hope to prepare a distinctive Herbal Lip gloss.

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INTRODUCTION

The word 'cosmetics' is derived from Greek word "kosmetikos" which means 'to adorn'. Since the early days materials used for beautification or improvement of appearance comes under the group of cosmetics. People want good-looking and the concept of cosmetics is as old as mankind and civilization. Generally, cosmetic products are referred to as care substances which can be made of chemical compounds or natural substances to enhance appearance and of human body^[1].

The main goal of such products is to maintain the body in good condition, protect it from the effects of the environment and aging process, change its appearance, and make the body smell nicer^[2]. Even though there is a booming success in the cosmetic industry, the actual meaning of cosmetics is misunderstood in many Western countries as mere makeup products. US Food and Drug Administration defines cosmetics as "products that are intended to be applied to the human body for beautifying, cleansing, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance without affecting the body's structure or functions"^[2]. As per this definition, any product which matches the above statement becomes a cosmetic product.

As the aesthetic appeal in the young generation is rising, the penetration of color cosmetics products dealing with eye, facial, and lip makeup categories in the Indian market is increasing^[3]. In the Asian region, India is estimated as one of the fastest-growing countries, in terms of color cosmetics.

Classification of Cosmetics^[4]:

Varieties of cosmetic preparations are used which can be classified as follows:

- **According to the region of use**

Skin: Powder, lipstick, rouge, creams, lotion, and solutions, etc.

Hair: Shampoo, conditioner, creams, bleach, coloring preparations, etc.

Nails: Nail lacquers, lacquer remover, etc.

Teeth: Powder, paste, gel, dentifrice, etc.

- **According to the function of cosmetic preparation**

Emollient preparations: cold cream, vanishing cream, foundation creams, etc.

Decorative preparations: Lipstick, rouge, eyeliner, lacquer etc..

Cleansing preparations: creams, shampoos and rinses etc

Deodorants /Antiperspirants: Spray, sticks, and mouthwashes etc

Protective preparations: Creams and powders

- **According to the physical form of cosmetics**

Powder: talcum powder, face powder

Emulsion: cold cream

Paste: tooth paste

Aerosol: shave spray

- **Adverse effects of Cosmetics^[1]**

Shampoo

Mild skin itching/irritation

Abnormal hair texture

Oiliness and dryness of hair and scalp

Hair thinning and temporary hair loss

Creams

Allergic reactions

Photosensitivity

Darkening of skin

Pimples

Face wash

Erythema

Skin Irritation

Peeling

Burning

Lip products

Cancer

Allergy

Renal failure

Hyperpigmentation

Hair Oil

Erythema

Itching

Scalp irritation

Eye irritation

Hair dyes

Skin damage

Allergic reactions

Eye exposure may cause loss of vision

Herbal Cosmetics

Herbal cosmetics are referred as beauty products which are formulated by using various herbal ingredients to provide a defined cosmetic benefit. Natural beauty is a blessing and cosmetics help in presenting and increasing the beauty and personality aspect of human beings^[5]. Herbal cosmetic products claimed to have efficacy and intrinsic acceptability due to regular use in daily life and avoid adverse effects which are commonly seen in synthetic products made of chemicals and other toxic ingredients. Indian herbs and their significance are quite popular. Herbal cosmetics have a growing demand in the global market and it is an invaluable gift of nature. Herbal formulations always have attracted considerable because of their good activity and having no side effects^[5]. The herbal cosmetics manufactured and used commonly for daily purposes include herbal facewash, herbal conditioner, herbal lipstick, herbal nail polish, herbal soap, herbal shampoo, etc^[5]. The industry is

now focusing on the growing segment with a vast scope of manifold expansion in the coming years.

Advantages of Herbal Cosmetics over Synthetic^[6]

Naturally available

Herbal cosmetics are made from herbs that are easily available from nature, they are free from all harmful synthetic chemicals. Although herbal cosmetics are prepared by naturally available plant parts and plant extracts, they may be as effective as synthetic products. e.g. aloe vera gel and coconut oil.

Safer to use

When compared to synthetic products, herbal cosmetics are less allergenic, nontoxic, tested and proven by dermatologists to be safe to use. Since they are made of natural ingredients.

Less side effects

Synthetic beauty products can irritate and cause rashes on skin. Herbal cosmetics are free from parabens that are suspected of interfering with hormone function.

Economical to use

Natural cosmetics are not that expensive. In fact, some of these products are more affordable than synthetic ones.

Wide selection

Various herbal products are available in the market for the preparation of herbal lip gloss. Selection of these herbs opens a wide range of possibilities in the

cosmetic industry. They demand more natural products with traceable and more natural ingredients, free from harmful chemicals and effectiveness. They may contain Azelaic acid, Lycopene, Vit- E, Vit- C, etc.

Herbal Lip gloss

Lip gloss is defined as “a cosmetic applied to the lips to provide a glossy finish and sometimes color”. It is distributed as a fluid or a soft solid substance that gives off a more pigmented color. Herbal lip gloss is defined as lip gloss made with herbal ingredients such as aloe vera, tomato, chamomile etc and fortified with antioxidant, Vit C, D, and E to hydrate lips. The product is available in range of opacity from translucent to solid and can have variously frosted, glittery, glossy, and metallic finishes. Herbal lip gloss is a cosmetic product containing pigments, oils, waxes, fragrances, preservatives, colors, texture, and protection to the lips.

The most common types of lip glosses are :

- Sheer Lip gloss
- Pigmented Lip gloss
- Shimmer Lip gloss
- Matte Lip gloss
- Glitter Lip gloss
- Plumping Lip gloss

Pros and Cons of Lip gloss^[7]

Table no :1

PROS	CONS
Glossy finish When it comes that alluring, glossy finish lipsticks cannot compete with a gloss hence the name lip gloss.	Can't Be Used For Lip Art The lip art looks with lipstick or other lip products can't be created with lip gloss
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application and Reapplication In the case of lipstick we need a lip brush for long-lasting effect and is a time-consuming method and requires smudging after applying it. That isn't the case with lip gloss.	Sticky This is one of the biggest demerits of lip gloss. Because it doesn't dry like other lip products, it's always sticky
Makes Your Lips Look Full As the lip gloss has a thicker texture than most other lip products, it can instantly make your lips look more full.	Not As Many Vivid Colors Lip gloss doesn't provide the same spectrum of colors that other lip products, like lip paint or lipstick make.
Lip Gloss Is Moisturizing Most lip products are identified for drying, but Lip glosses are so moisturizing hence don't have to worry about chapped lips in the winter.	

Anatomy of lips ^[8,9]

Lips are soft, movable body part at the mouth of humans and helps with the intake of food and speech. ‘‘Labium superius oris’’ and ‘‘Labium inferius oris’’, are the upper and lower lips respectively. The meeting point where the lips join the surrounding skin of the mouth area is the vermilion border and the reddish area within the border is called the vermilion zone. Cupid’s bow is the vermilion border of the upper lips. The fleshy protuberance located in the center of the upper lip is a tubercle known by various terms

including pyochelin (also spelled procheilon), the ‘‘tuberculum labii superioris’’, and the ‘‘labial tubercle’’. The skin of the lip, with three to five cellular layers, is very thin compared to typical face skin, which has up to 16 layers. With light skin color, the lip skin contains fewer melanocytes which give skin its color. Because of this, the blood vessels appear through the skin of the lips, which leads to their notable red coloring. With darker skin color this effect is less prominent, as in this case, the skin of the lips contains more melanin and thus is visually darker.

Fig 1: Anatomy of Lip

The skin of the lip forms the border between the exterior skin of the face and the interior mucous membrane of the inside of the mouth. The upper lip covers the anterior surface of the body of the maxilla. Its upper half is of the usual skin color and has a depression at its center, directly under the nasal septum, called the philtrum, which is Latin for lower nose, while its lower half is a markedly different, red-colored skin tone more similar to the color of the inside of the mouth, and the term vermilion refers to the colored portion of either the upper or lower lip.

Market Research of Lip Gloss

Lip Gloss Market Overview:

The whole lip gloss market is driven by the launch of some attractive & innovative products which can easily gain the attraction of customers^[10]. This analysis

report offers detailed information regarding the current market condition, latest trends & key players, as well as the overall industrial environment throughout the world. The global Lip Gloss Market size is projected to reach approximately USD 4.51 Billion by 2027, at a CAGR of 4.90% from 2020 to 2027^[11]. While females have long used these types of primary products, further unprotected sun exposure of the lips can cause wrinkling, premature aging, or actinic cheilitis. There is an increasing demand for sun protection lip care products. Although manufacturers & investors have increased their attention on product innovation, the development of long-lasting and fast-acting formulas has also increased significantly.

Fig no:2

The biggest challenge for the lip gloss business sector

Lip gloss has been trending globally among both men and women. Lip gloss with vivid colors are expected to be the future of lip products. According to the demands of customers, it has been seen that the number of production industry has increased significantly in the last few years. Due to this, the competition within these industries have has increased immensely.

Covid -19 Analysis^[11] :

Due to covid-19 epidemic, almost every company has been facing huge number of losses in their business. The global cash market & stocks have been lost massively. In addition, the lip gloss market share has also faced the same crisis due to covid-19 or the lockdown period. Besides this, the whole market size has stopped production for a sometime which the shareholders & the investors have faced a huge loss due to the stoppage of production.

Chief factors Existing in the market:

Key Market Drivers:

Whenever the market opens, some lip gloss markets merge & collaborate with investors to decide to generate more production manufacturing plants which help more key players to add to the industry.

Market Challenges:

is the loss of production during the covid-19. Along with this, every company has been continuously trying to overcome this situation. This was one of the biggest challenges for the lip gloss market sector.

Market opportunities:

After opening the market of covid-19, the investors have analyzed and gotten an idea about some opportunities of engaging with the partners & collaborate with them to invest the amounts on making this business sector.

Market Segmentation:

The lip gloss market segmentation has been divided into four main categories: finish, categories, distribution chain and regional. In terms of the finish section, the lip gloss market has been further divided into four categories like glossy, matte, glitter & others. According to the categories list, it is divided into 2 main sections: conventional & organic or natural. The distributional channel is further divided into two categories store-based & non-store-based. There are four main sections in the regional category like North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific & Rest of the world.

Regional Analysis^[10] :

- Growth will originate from Europe during the forecast period.

- Germany, France, and the UK are the key markets for the lip gloss market in Europe.
- Market growth in this region will be faster than the growth of the market in North America, South America, and MEA.
- The growing female population in the region will

facilitate the lip gloss market growth in Europe over the forecast period.

COMPANY

Lip products have always been one of the most important cosmetics used by women in India. The latest trend in the lip color market is lip gloss.^[12]

Table no :2 List of Top Brands in India

SYNTHETIC	HERBAL
Lakme	Himalaya
Maybelline	Deyga
Revlon	Biotique
M.A.C	Mamaearth
Sugar	Plum
Loreal	Khadi
Elle	Vilvah
Faces Canada	Soultree

Cosmeceuticals^[13]

Cosmeceuticals are a combination of cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. Cosmeceuticals are cosmetic products with biologically active ingredients having medical or drug-like benefits. Cosmeceuticals are used to improve and nourish the skin's appearance and are known to treat various dermatologic conditions. Herbs used in cosmeceuticals are given below :

Tomato

Tomato can be used as a natural remedy for various skin concerns. They contain antioxidants, vitamin C, vitamin A, vitamin B, lycopene, carotenoids. B vitamins also contribute to cell repair. They may reduce hyperpigmentation and sun damage.

Potato

Potatoes are the underground tubers that grows on the roots of the potato plant, *Solanum tuberosum*. Potatoes comes with a plethora of essential nutrients such as vitamins C, B1 and B6, various minerals, antioxidants and an enzyme Catecholase. The natural bleaching properties of potatoes diminishes pigmentation, dark spots, marks and blemishes. An enzyme present in potato called Catecholase can help to manage hyperpigmentation.

Aloe

Aloe vera is a herbal plant species obtained from *Aloe barbadensis miller* which belongs to Asphodelaceae (Liliceae) family. Aloe vera gel also comprises vitamins, amino acids, minerals and enzymes, which provide its skin-soothing effect.

Aloe vera gel has great moisturising properties and forms a protective film for the skin, which helps give it its healing properties. It has analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities..

Beetroot

Beetroot are rich in vitamin C, folate (vitamin B9), minerals, betalains etc. Betalains acts as the coloring agent and provide bleaching properties in beetroot. Besides lightening of the lip color, they also nourishes the lips by locking the moisture in.

Carrot

Carrot is obtained from the plant *Daucus carota* that belongs to family Apiaceae. It is a valuable herb since ages as due to its richness in Vitamin A, Vitamin E, β -carotene, and lesser amounts of α -carotene. Carrot helps repair skin tissues while also protecting skin from harmful radiation

Turmeric

Turmeric is obtained from *Curcuma longa* of the family Zingiberaceae. Turmeric contains a wide range of phytochemicals including- demethoxycurcumin, curcumol, eugenol, tetrahydrocurcumin, curcumin, turmerin etc. Curcumin is the phytochemical that imparts yellow color to turmeric and is responsible for most of the therapeutic effects. Uses of turmeric include antiseptic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimalarial, insect repellent, and other activities associated to turmeric.

Pomegranate

Pomegranates are accepted as a super food as they advantage in your body both internally and

externally because they contain high levels of antioxidants ever discovered in a fruit. Pomegranates are a common ingredient in Ayurvedic medicine because they are rich in fibers, minerals, folic acid,

and vitamins A, C, and E. It has benefits like rich in antioxidants, cellular regeneration, sun protection, anti-aging, youthful skin, dry skin, oily skin.

Table no: 3

INGREDIENTS	IMPORTANCE
Bees Wax	Moisturizer, Hardness, Glossy Appearance
Paraffin Wax	Hardness, Glossy Appearance
Olive Oil	Moisturizer, Antioxidant
Coconut Oil	Moisturizer, Hardness
Almond Oil	Emollient, Skin rejuvenation, Moisturizer
Vitamin E Oil	Moisturizer, Emollient, Skin rejuvenation
Tomato Seed Oil	Remove dead cells, Heal dry lips, Treat hyperpigmentation
Potato Extract	Treat Hyperpigmentation, Scars, Skin brightening
Colouring Agent	Provide color
Flavouring Agent	Provide flavour

FORMULATION OF HERBAL LIP GLOSS

Common Ingredients used in Natural Lip Gloss Formulation^[14]

The list of materials used as key formulation ingredients for natural lip gloss given in the table below:

Table no :4

BASE	OIL	COLOURING AGENT	FLAVOURING AGENT
Cocoa Butter	Coconut oil	Beetroot	Raspberry
Olive Butter	Olive oil	Pomegranate	Strawberry
Shea wax	Almond oil	Lemon	Honey
White Bees wax	Vitamin E oil	Tomato	Pineapple
Yellow Bees wax	Peanut oil	Watermelon	Rosemary
Carnauba wax	Tea tree oil	Honey	Lemon
Candelilla wax	Glycerin	Saffron	Apricot
Mango Butter	Castor oil	Turmeric	Cherry
Avacado Butter	Jojoba oil	Capsicum	Jasmine
Jojoba wax	Grape seed oil	Cherry	Rose oil

Waxes^[15]

A mixture of waxes is employed to achieve desired melting point, viscosity and other physical properties of the gloss. The wax give the lip gloss its consistency and ease of application.

Bees Wax: Beeswax has been used topically on the skin since ancient Egyptian times. It softens and lubricates skin prevents water loss and has antiseptic properties. Wax provides a protective barrier to the

skin and it contain vitamin A, which helps skin regenerate sooner after damage^[16].

Candelilla Wax: It is one of the hardest waxes, so it provides good strength and raises melting point. 5 – 20 % which is obtained from candelilla plant and is produced in Mexico by immersing the plant in a boiling water containing sulphuric acid and skimming off the wax that rises to the surface.

Lanolin : 5 – 15%

Oils^[22]

Oils not only give lips a beautiful glossy shine, but they also nourish, soften, and protect your lips from dehydration and cracking. Lip oils are composed of oils from ingredients such as almond, olive, coconut, avocado, castor oil.

Olive Oil: It is very effective as a moisturizer. It's also been used to treat minor skin problems like acne and is also effective in healing wounds and burns.

Coconut oil: It is produced by crushing copra, the dried kernel, which contains about 60-65% of the oil. Coconut oil is excellent as a skin moisturizer and softener.

Jjoba oil : Jojoba oil is easily refined to remove any odor, color it is oxidatively stable, and is often used in cosmetics as a moisturizer and as a carrier oil for exotic fragrances. Jojoba oil contains oodles of vitamins, antioxidants, and anti-inflammatory properties.

Essential oil: Essential oils are aromatic, volatile

liquids obtained from plant material through steam distillation and named after the plant from which they are derived. Some of the most popular essential oils includes lavender, peppermint, tea tree, lemon, sweet orange.

Coloring agent^[17]

Colorants or coloring agents are mainly used to impart a distinctive appearance to the Cosmetic products .The color is imparted to the lips in two ways; (a) By staining the skin with a solution of dyestuff which can penetrate the outer layer of the lip skin, (b) By covering the lips with a colored layer which serves to hide any skin roughness and give a smooth appearance^[18].The colorant derived from natural source should be nontoxic with no physiological activity .Colorants should be unaffected by light, tropical temperatures, hydrolysis and micro-organisms and therefore they must be stable on storage^[23]

Table no. 5

COLOR	PLANT SOURCE
White-tan	Potato , Onion, Banana
Yellow orange	Papaya, Pineapple, Peach, Carrot, Orange
Red	Beetroot, Tomato, Strawberry, Pomegranate

Flavouring Agent^[17]

Flavouring agents are an essential component to mask the odour and taste of the fatty or waxbase as well as to impart an attractive flavor. Flavours used in lip gloss should not contain any ingredient which may be irritating or toxic.

Table no. 6

TASTE	MASKING FLAVOUR
Salt	Butter scotch , Maple
Bitter	Wild cherry, Walnut, Chocolate mint, Liquorice
Sweet	Fruit Berry , Vanilla
Acid	Citrus

METHOD OF PREPARATION^[19]

- Preparation of Lip Gloss Base**^[24]

Accurately weighed waxes and oils are transferred to a beaker.To which chosen essential oils and dye are added and mixed well until no fine particles are to be seen.

- Preparation of Lavender Lip Gloss**

Many organic products like tomato seed oil,Almond oil, vitamin E can help keep lips hydrated and healthy when used in the preparation. These ingredients can promote regular lip gloss into sun protectant lip gloss ,Lip lightening lip gloss ,Lip plumping lip gloss and so much more. Presence of Tomato seed oil, Cinnamon

oil, Almond oil and Olive oil gives lip lightening, lip plumping, lips hydrating and nourishing effects respectively.

Procedure

- Weigh accurately all the ingredients according to the formula.
- Transfer 1.84 gm of cocoa butter and 1gm bees wax to a clean glass beaker.
- Add weighed amount of 1.5ml olive oil and 3.5ml almond oil into it and place it in water bath.
- Stir occasionally and mix well. Heat until it gets completely melted.
- After that remove it from heat and allow to cool.

- Then add required amount of tomato seed oil, cinnamon essential oil and lavender essential oil. Mix well until they are completely incorporated with the base.
- Then add Vitamin E to the base and stir well.
- Finally add the dye (mica powder) and mix well.
- Transfer the prepared lip gloss into the lip gloss container.
- Other alternatives:

Table no . 7

METHOD 1 (Mango Lip Gloss)	METHOD 2 (Beetroot Lip gloss)	METHOD 3 (Carrot Lip gloss)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Bees Wax •Virgin Coconut oil •Mango butter •Jojoba Oil •Grape fruit essential oil Dye 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Bees Wax •Coconut oil •Castor oil •Jojoba oil •Vitamin E oil •Glycerine Beetroot powder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cera alba •Castor oil •Vitamin E oil •Carrot oil •Soy Lecithin Carmine dye

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

The Evaluation studies are important in order to determine the efficiency, stability and the consistency of finished products. The evaluation tests are as follows :

➤ Physical appearance

The physical appearance of developed formulations was checked for color, texture and consistency. Observations were reported.

➤ Determination of pH^[20]

The pH of lip gloss was determined in order to investigate the possibility of any side effect. As an acidic or alkaline pH may cause irritation of lips, it was determined to keep the pH of lip gloss as close to neutral as possible i.e, 7.2. This would not cause any irritation to lips. The pH study was carried out by dissolving 1gm of sample into 100 ml water. The pH measurement was done using pH meter.

➤ Test of spreadability^[21]

The 100mg product is applied repeatedly onto the glass slide (at room temperature) to visually observe the uniformity and kept for five minutes. The following criteria were established for this test :

- G – Good, uniform, does not leave fragments and no deformation on application
- I – Intermediate , uniform ,leaves few fragments and little deformation .
- B – Bad , not uniform ,leaves many fragments

,difficult application and intensedeformation.

➤ Light Exposure Testing

The product and packaging can be sensitive to UV radiation .

- ✓ All products should placed in glass and the actual packaging in the window andif its available a light box that has a broad spectrum output .
- ✓ Place another glass jars completely covered with aluminium foil in the windowto serve as a control .
- ✓ Allow to stand for a particular period of time.
- ✓ Observe whether there is discoloration on product or package .
- ✓ This discoloration is may due to the fragrance or some other sensitive ingredients.

➤ Melting Point Determination Test ^[20]

- ✓ The determination of melting point is done in order to determine the storage propertiesof the product .
- ✓ Ideal melting point of lip gloss should be 60°C.

➤ Test for Rancidity

- ✓ The oxidation of oil such as castor oil and many other ingredients may results bad odor and taste and also result sticky product.
- ✓ The test for rancidity can be done using hydrogen peroxide and determining its peroxide number.

➤ Determination of color dispersion^[20]

The test is done in order to determine the uniform dispersion of colour particle .The size of the particle

is determined by the light microscopic studies and it should not be more than 50u.

RESULTS:

➤ Physical appearance

The physical appearance of developed formulations was checked for color, odour and consistency. Observations were reported.

Colour : Red, **Odour :** Lavender, **Consistency :** Running Consistency

➤ Determination of pH

The pH measurement was done using pH meter. Ideal value should be between 5 to 6 (Ph of lips). Observed value of lip gloss is 5.5.

➤ Determination of color dispersion

The test is done in order to determine the uniform dispersion of colour particle .The size of the particle is determined by the light microscopic studies and was not more than 50u.

➤ Test of spreadability

Spreadability test was performed and the sample was found to be having good spreadability.

G – Good, uniform, does not leave fragments and no deformation on application .

➤ Light Exposure Testing

Light exposure test was carried no discoloration or change was observed.

➤ Melting Point Determination Test

The determination of melting point was done and melting point of lip gloss was found to be 60°C.

Scope

Herbal cosmetics are prepared using permissible

cosmetics ingredients to form the base in which one or more herbal ingredients are used to treat different skin ailments and beautification. The chemical formulation of all these cosmetics products includes addition of various natural additives like waxes, oil, natural color, natural fragrances, and parts of plants like leaves, etc. Cosmetics products are the best option to reduce skin problems such as hyperpigmentation, skin wrinkling, skin aging and rough skin texture, etc. The usage of herbal cosmetics has increased to many folds in the personal care system and there is a great demand for herbal cosmetics. The use of bioactive ingredients in cosmetics influences the biological function of skin and provides nutrients necessary for healthy skin. The advantages of herbal cosmetics are low cost, side effects free, environment friendly, and safe to use. Also has a great future ahead as compared to synthetic cosmetics. Proper regulation of these herbs and standardization will lead to tremendous and significant growth in the herbal cosmetic field. There is tremendous scope to launch numerous herbal cosmetics using appropriate bioactive ingredients with a suitable fatty oil, essential oils, protective and additives.

CONCLUSION:

The selected topic regarding cosmetic science covers broad area on various concepts of herbal cosmetics followed by their comparison with synthetic cosmetics. This study provides information regarding formulation, preparation and evaluation of herbal lip gloss as well as the current and future market scope of herbal lip gloss.

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